

Parkinson's Disease Model

Creative Bioarray is an innovative biotechnology company whose mission focuses on developing unique technologies.

Our Services

- ✓ Neurotoxic Models
- ✓ Genetic Models
- ✓ Service Available

Why Choose Us

We help customers evaluate drug efficacy and study the pathology of Parkinson's disease through *in vivo/in vitro* PD models.

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disease, affecting 1% of the population over 55 years of age. Pathologically, PD is the result of selective degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the Substantia Nigra, which causes decreased levels of dopamine in the striatum and leads to abnormal motor control.

Motor symptoms in PD patients include bradykinesia, muscle tone rigidity, resting tremor, and postural instability; non-motor symptoms such as sleep disturbance, dementia, sensory abnormalities, and autonomic dysfunction.

Neurological disorders can be modeled in animals to recreate specific pathogenic events and behavioral outcomes. In addition, PD is a heterogeneous disease with varying ages of onset, symptoms, and rates of progression. This heterogeneity requires the use of a variety of animal models to study different aspects of the disease.

Neurotoxic Models

6-Hydroxydopamine

- ✓ 6-OHDA is the classic and oft-utilized toxin-based animal model of PD. Despite its limitations, this model has contributed greatly to our understanding of PD pathology.
- ✓ 6-OHDA may be the endogenous toxin that triggers the neurodegenerative process of PD. As a neurotoxin, it does produce damage in the nigrostriatal DA pathway.

MPTP

Currently, MPTP represents the most important and most frequently used Parkinsonian toxin applied in animal models. It is used mainly in nonhuman primates and mice but has also been used in many other species such as dogs and cats.

MPTP is highly lipophilic and rapidly crosses the blood-brain barrier after systemic administration. It can be administered by a variety of regimens, but the most common and reproducible form is still systemic injection (subcutaneous, intravenous).

Paraquat

Paraquat (N, N'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium) (PQ) is an herbicide widely used in agriculture that resembles MPP+.

PQ's importance to PD research is its ability to induce increases in α -synuclein in individual DA neurons in the SNpc and its ability to induce LB-like structures in DA neurons of the SNpc.

Rotenone

Unlike PQ, which is a pure herbicide rotenone, is both an herbicide and an insecticide.

The apparent beauty of this model is that, like paraquat, it seems to replicate almost all of the hallmarks of PD including causing α -synuclein aggregation and Lewy-like body formation.

Genetic Models

α -Synuclein

α -Synuclein is a small protein (at the size of 14 kDa) that is present abundantly in the pre-synaptic terminals.

Mutations of α -Synuclein have been characterized in the inherited form of PD, for instance, substitutions (A53T, A30P, and E46K), duplication, or triplication. Importantly, α -Synuclein is identified as the major building block of Lewy Bodies (LBs).

Leucine-Rich Repeat Kinase 2 (LRRK2)

- ✓ LRRK2 mutations are associated with an autosomal dominant pattern of inheritance in familial PD.
- ✓ G2019S and R1441C/G are the two most common LRRK2 mutations. Other LRRK2 models have been created using viral vectors such as herpes simplex virus (HSV) and adenoviral vectors.

Protein De-glycose (DJ-1)

- ✓ DJ-1 mutations have been known to be associated with recessive forms of familial parkinsonism. Several studies suggest that DJ-1 is an antioxidant protein, which is useful in counteracting the oxidative environment of DA neurons.
- ✓ DJ-1 knockout mice could be a valuable tool to study the molecular mechanism of PD.

Pten-Induced Kinase 1 (PINK1)

- ✓ Mutations in Pten-induced kinase 1 (PINK1) are associated with recessive parkinsonism.
- ✓ PINK1 is a neuroprotective kinase found primarily in the mitochondria and cytosolic compartments and plays a role in neuronal differentiation.

Service Available

Creative Bioarray focuses on drug research and development services and helps customers assess the drug efficacy and study the associated pathological mechanisms of Parkinson's disease by *in vivo/vitro*

[PD model.](#)

- ✓ Establish models with a high success rate and suitable for a specific project
- ✓ Behavioral testing
- ✓ Neuronal Morphology Evaluation
- ✓ Neurobiochemical evaluation
- ✓ Histopathology assays
- ✓ Mechanism/signaling pathway studies
- ✓ Biomarkers discovery

Reference

1. Raza C, *et al.* (2019). "Parkinson's disease: Mechanisms, translational models and management strategies." *Life Sci.* 226, 77-90.
2. Chia SJ, *et al.* (2020). "Historical Perspective: Models of Parkinson's Disease." *Int J Mol Sci.* 21 (7), 2464.